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Bibliometric Analysis of Studies on the Use of Digital Twins in Disasters

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ABSTRACT

Disasters are events that cause serious property, life and social losses around the world every year and that stop or interrupt people's normal lives. Disasters are classified according to their cause as natural disasters, man-made disasters and technology-induced disasters. As is the case all over the world, our country is also seriously affected by disasters. Considering the seriousness of the situation, the importance of scientific studies in this field is increasing. The aim of this study is to examine the studies conducted using digital twins on disasters. For this purpose, the bibliometric analysis method was used. The sample of the study consists of scientific publications scanned in the Web of Science (WoS) database between 2012-2025. 226 studies were obtained from a total of 167 sources. “Applied Sciences-Basel” and “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction” are in first place with 9 publications at publishing scientific studies using digital twins in disasters. Among scientific sources, the source that published the most studies in 2025 is the “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction”. The author who published the most articles in the field of using digital twins in disasters is “UY” with 8 articles. The year in which the institutions published the most is 2025, and the institution with the most publications in 2025 is “Texas A&M University”.

1 INTRODUCTION

The disaster can be defined as ‘serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society at any scale due to hazardous events interacting with conditions of exposure, vulnerability and capacity, leading to one or more of the following: human, material, economic and environmental losses and impacts’ [1]. Disasters are divided into three categories, natural disasters, man-made disasters and technology-induced disasters, based on the sources that cause them. The types of

disasters observed in the world are geological disasters, climatic disasters, biological disasters, social disasters and technological disasters [2]. Disasters cause serious losses every year both in our country and around the world. Therefore, it is of great importance to take measures to prevent or minimize disasters and their effects.

Digital twin is a technology developed to create a high-accuracy copy of a physical object, system or process in a virtual environment. The virtual model is created by continuously providing real-time data about the physical model to the system as input with the help of technologies such as sensors and the Internet of Things (IoT). Since digital twin technology simulates the real-time behavior of the system, it offers the opportunity to examine how the system works under different conditions [3].

It is widely accepted that digital and intelligent technologies can provide solutions to the fundamental problems (disaster prevention and reduction, rescue and recovery) in disaster risk management [4]. Digital twin technology has also been used extensively in disaster-related studies in recent years. Astarita et al. conducted a bibliometric analysis to examine how digital twins are used in risk management in cities [5]. Mahammad Yousuf et al. examined how digital twins are used in infrastructure robustness assessment and disaster management [6]. Inyang and Taghikhah presented a general review of studies using digital twin-based decision support systems in disaster management [7]. Hlal et al. reviewed studies using digital twins in urban flood risk management using the PRISMA 2020 framework [8]. In this study, studies on the use of digital twins in disasters were examined using bibliometric analysis method, considering the current importance of the subject.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

Bibliometric analysis is one of the popular literature screening methods used to examine and analyze large amounts of scientific data. This method summarizes a large amount of bibliometric data to provide the status of the intellectual structure of a research subject or field and the tendencies of the field [9]. In this study, bibliometric analysis was performed using Bibliometrix software, a package of R program. Web of Science database was used for scientific publication search. Scientific publication search was carried out by scanning of search query "Digital Twin*" OR "Digital Model" OR "Virtual Twin" OR "Virtual Model" (Topic) and "Disaster*" (Topic). In the Web of Science, searching on the "Topic" means searching for title, abstract, keyword plus, and author keywords. Only English publications were included in the research. In the search between 2012-2025, a total of 226 publications for the use of digital twin in disasters were reached. After downloading the publications in Bibtex format, necessary analyzes were made using Bibliometrix software.

3 RESULTS

Figure 1. An Overview of Studies related to Use of Digital Twins in Disasters

The time period of the study was determined as from 2012 to the present. 226 studies were obtained from a total of 167 sources. It was observed that the annual increase rate of studies on this subject is %32.55, a total of 946 authors are included in these studies, the number of single-authored studies is 11, and the international co-authorship rate in the studies is %29.2. It was found that the number of co-authors per study is 4.73, the number of keywords used by the authors is 10806, the average age of the studies is 2.29, and the average number of citations per study is 12.18 (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Annual scientific production related to use of digital twins in disasters

Figure 3: Average citations per year related to use of digital twins in disasters

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the annual change in scientific publication production and the average number of citations per year, respectively.

Figure 4: A sankey diagram related to use of digital twins in disasters

Figure 4 is a Sankey diagram consisting of three fields. Respectively the first field (CR), the second field (AU) and the third field (KW_Merged) represent Cited References, Authors and Keywords. This diagram shows the connections between the most cited references, contributing authors, and dominant keywords in the researches related to the use of digital twins in disasters.

Figure 5: Most relevant sources related to use of digital twins in disasters

Figure 5 shows the sources that publish scientific studies using digital twins in disasters. While “Applied Sciences-Basel” and “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction” are in first place with 9 publications, “Buildings” journal is in second place with 8 publications.

Figure 6: Most local cited sources related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Local Cited Sources” is a measure that shows the sources most frequently cited by other sources in the studied dataset. Figure 6 shows the most frequently cited sources in studies on the use

Figure 8: Source local impact by h-index related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Source Local Impact by H-Index” refers to a measure that shows how effective the analyzed sources are in a certain study are according to the h-index measure. Figure 8 shows that the most effective source in the field of using digital twins in disasters, according to the h-index, is the “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction” with an impact factor of 7, and the second most effective source is “Buildings” with an impact factor of 6.

Figure 9: Source' production over time related to use of digital twins in disasters

"Source' Production Over Time" is a measure of how many scientific studies are published per year in each source. As can be seen from Figure 9, the number of scientific studies published by all sources is at its highest level in 2025. Among scientific sources, the source that published the most studies in 2025 is the “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction”.

Figure 10: Most relevant authors related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Relevant Authors” shows the ranking of the authors who contributed the most to the research field under consideration. Figure 10 shows that the author who published the most articles in the field of using digital twins in disasters is “UY” with 8 articles, and the authors who published the second most articles are “HAM Y” and “PARK S” with 6 articles each.

Figure 11: Most Local Cited Authors related to Use of Digital Twins in Disasters

"Most Locally Cited Authors" is a metric that shows the most cited authors in the studied dataset. As can be seen in Figure 11, the number of citations received by all authors in the studied dataset is 0.

Figure 12: Authors' production over time related to use of digital twins in disasters

"Authors' Production over Time" is a measure of how many scientific publications produces each author in the studied dataset per year. This measure demonstrates the authors' scientific production performance. While darkening blue circles indicate the total number of citations per year, darkening of circles indicates an increase in the number of citations. While the growing blue circles show the number of articles, and the growth of the circles indicates that the number of articles increase. "UY", stands out as the most productive writer from 2018 to 2025, with 7 articles (Figure 12).

Figure 13: Author productivity through Lotka's law related to use of digital twins in disasters

Lotka's Law describes how author productivity is distributed within a research field. The basic logic of the law is that most authors publish only one article, fewer publish two, fewer still publish three, and so on. This situation is also seen in Figure 13.

Figure 14: Authors’ local impact by h index related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Authors’ Local Impact by H Index” is a measure that shows how influential each author is in the studied dataset using the h-index. This measure focuses only on the authors' publications and citations in the studied dataset, not on all of their studies. As can be seen from Figure 14, while the most influential author is “Park S” with an h-index of 5, and the second most influential authors are “Chen G”, “Ham Y” and “Kim J” with an h-index of 4.

Figure 15: Most relevant affiliations related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Relevant Affiliations” is a measure that shows the institutions (universities, laboratories, companies, etc.) of the researchers with the most publications in the studied dataset. As can be seen from Figure 15, the institution with the most publications according to this measure is “Texas A&M University” with 36 publications, and the institution with the second most publications is “China University Petroleum” with 14 publications.

Figure 16: Affiliations’ production over time related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Affiliations’ Production over Time” is a measure that shows how many publications each institution makes per year in the studied dataset. Figure 16 shows that the year in which the institutions published the most is 2025, and the institution with the most publications in 2025 is “Texas A&M University”.

Figure 17: Corresponding author’s countries related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Corresponding Author’s Countries” is a measure that shows which countries the corresponding authors of the articles in the studied dataset are affiliated with. Figure 17 shows that while the country that produces the most publications individually and ranks first in the corresponding author ranking is China, the country that produces the most publications in collaboration with other countries and ranks second in the corresponding author ranking is the USA.

Figure 18: Country production over time related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Country Production over Time” is a measure that shows how many publications are made each year by authors from different countries in the studied dataset. Figure 18 shows that the scientific publication production of all countries have reached its highest level in 2025, and the country that produced the most publications in 2025 is China.

Figure 19: Most cited countries related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Cited Countries” is a measure that shows the countries of the authors of the articles that are most cited across all sources globally. Figure 19 shows that the most cited country is the USA with 904 citations, and the second most cited country is China with 410 citations.

Figure 20: Most global cited documents related to use of digital twins in disasters

"Most Globally Cited Documents" shows the individual documents (articles, etc.) in the studied dataset that are most cited globally, not only in the studied dataset but across all sources. Figure 20 shows that the most cited article, with 295 citations, was written by “Adel A.”, while the second most cited article, with 221 citations, was written by “Fan C.”.

Figure 21: Most local cited documents related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Locally Cited Documents” shows individual articles in the studied dataset that are most cited by other articles in the same dataset. Figure 21 shows that none of the articles in the studied dataset cite each other.

Figure 22: Most local cited references related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Local Cited References” shows the specific references (from the reference lists of the articles in the dataset) that are most frequently cited in the studied dataset. Figure 22 shows that “Ford Dn.” is the most cited reference with 22 citations, and “Ham Y.” is the second most cited reference with 16 citations.

Figure 23: Reference publication year spectroscopy related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Reference Publication Year Spectroscopy” is a metric that analyzes the publication years of the most frequently cited references in the across the entire dataset examined. This measure breaks down citation years into peaks to find important historical publications in the field under study. This situation is seen in Figure 23.

Figure 24: Most relevant words related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Most Relevant Words” shows the most frequently used important words in the titles, abstracts or keywords of the publications in the studied dataset. As can be seen from Figure 24, while “digital twin” used in 68 publications ranks first, “digital twins” used in 28 publications ranks second.

Figure 25: The word cloud related to use of digital twins in disasters

Figure 25 is a word cloud visualization of the “Most Relevant Words” in the studied dataset. The size of each word reflects how often it appears in the titles, abstracts, or keywords of publications in the studied dataset.

Figure 26: The treemap related to use of digital twins in disasters

The treemap shown in Figure 26 provides a structured and detailed view of the “Most Relevant Words” in the studied dataset. Treemap is a treemap visualization of the most frequently used words in the studied dataset, just like the previous word cloud. Unlike a word cloud, a treemap includes absolute numbers, percentages of the total, and size and color that reflect importance and frequency.

Figure 27: Words' frequency over time related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Words’ Frequency over Time” is a measure of how often certain words appear in article titles, abstracts, or keywords over a selected time period. Figure 27 shows that the most used word between 2021 and 2025 is “Digital Twin”.

Figure 28: Trend topics related to use of digital twins in disasters

“Trend Topics” shows how certain keywords related to research topics of interest have emerged and how their popularity has increased or decreased over a certain period of time. Figure 28 shows the evolution (emergence and popularity) of research themes in the field of digital twin use in disasters over time. The circles in the figure increase in size as the number of appearances of the research themes in the relevant time periods increases.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, studies on the use of digital twins in disasters were examined using bibliometric analysis method. The time period of the study was determined as from 2012 to the present. 226 studies were obtained from a total of 167 sources. “Applied Sciences-Basel” and “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction” are in first place with 9 publications at publishing scientific studies using digital twins in disasters. The most effective source in the field of using digital twins in disasters, according to the h-index, is the “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction” with an impact factor of 7. Among scientific sources, the source that published the most studies in 2025 is the “International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction”. The author who published the most articles in the field of using digital twins in disasters is “UY” with 8 articles, and the authors who published the second most articles are “HAM Y” and “PARK S” with 6 articles each. “UY”, stands out as the most productive writer from 2018 to 2025, with 7 articles. The year in which the institutions published the most is 2025, and the institution with the most publications in 2025 is “Texas A&M University”. The scientific publication production of all countries have reached its highest level in 2025, and the country that produced the most publications in 2025 is China. In the “Most Relevant Words” category, while “digital twin” used in 68 publications ranks first, “digital twins” used in 28 publications ranks second.

The limitation of the study is that the 226 articles found in the database as a result of the publication search were not subjected to an additional review to determine whether they were fully appropriate for the subject. In future studies, the number of databases used for publication scanning can be increased and additional examination can be conducted to check whether the publications are fully relevant to the topic.

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